

Research Across Disciplinary Boundaries: Data Challenges and Solutions in the Environmental and Eco-social Sciences

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Summary. The synthesis of data across disciplinary domains is required to achieve desperately needed understanding about modern, complex, global challenges. Complex questions in today's world such as the challenges of climate change, carry with them a complex range of data, all of which need to be harmonised to permit analysis. In the PARSEC project [1], a team of synthesis and data scientists has been assembled from across the globe. We come from varying disciplines, including data science, the management of protected areas, ecology, remote sensing, AI, sociology, economics, and modelling. We discuss some of our solutions to enable successful collaboration as we: (1) blend data of different scales, time-frames and types; (2) work together across large geographic boundaries; and (3) ensure the data management is of international standard from the beginning of the project to publication.

Keywords. inter-disciplinary, PARSEC, DDOMP, data sharing, workflow

1 Introduction

The PARSEC project (Building New Tools for Data Sharing and Re-use through a Transnational Investigation of the Socioeconomic Impacts of Protected Areas [1]) has a unique cross-cutting objective: to conduct interdisciplinary, transnational synthesis science while developing and testing novel approaches to the management and preservation of environmental and socioeconomic data. PARSEC is funded through the Science-driven e-Infrastructure Innovation (SEI) Collaborative Research Action of the Belmont Forum [2] by four countries, Japan, the USA, France and Brazil, with associates from Australia, the UK and elsewhere. The project provides a unique insight into the challenges of: (1) blending data of different scales, time frames and types; (2) working together across large geographic

boundaries; and (3) ensuring data management is to international standards from the start to publication.

2 Challenges and solutions

Our scientific objective is to detect changes in the socio-economic status of communities in the environs of Protected Areas (PA's) in response to the creation of the PA. We are using remotely sensed spatial data, trained using Artificial Intelligence techniques to detect changes in detectable spatial characteristics that have socio-economic meaning.

2.1 Blending data of different scales, time frames and types

To analyse the impact of PAs on nearby regions we are using a data science framework (Figure 1) whose central machinery is a deep neural

network model to map inputs to outputs. We are accessing data from several sources such as geostatistical national census data, which is at different spatial and temporal scale and resolution from the remotely sensed data, e.g. from decades for the socio-economic data, to days for the remote-sensed data. The first challenge, therefore, is to disaggregate these heterogeneous data to establish a common granularity which can be used across countries. We need the most fine-grained data available, but there will be various cycles to refine the main goal, and we may need to adjust the granularity to reveal the relationships.

Figure 1: Proposed workflow to handle acquisition from different scales and types. A common data granularity, as fine as possible, will be used to annotate the satellite image data, and then inputted into the deep learning model for training and testing.

storage. Amazon EC2 will be used for machine learning experiments, and a GitHub account [4] has been created to handle versioning.

An important aspect of co-working in a transnational consortium is good communication. As well as email, we have a system of regular Zoom meetings, multiple Slack channels, a dedicated Google Drive and a Zotero community. Time zone differences dictate the use of multiple communication modes (verbal, written, synchronous and asynchronous).

2.3 Ensuring data management is of international standard.

2.2 Working across geographic boundaries.

The project relies on co-ordinated practice across the project teams, who conduct different components of the analysis. Development of algorithms is primarily occurring in France, but the workflows and large data sets need to be shared with the other teams safely, robustly, and in a timely manner. We intend to use Amazon Web Services (AWS) infrastructure, for its substantial working space, AWS Organization to create team space, and AWS Lake Formation for satellite image

The PARSEC project, as a grantee of the Belmont Forum, is required to implement the new Data and Digital Output Management Plan (DDOMP) format [3, 5]. One of the objectives of PARSEC is to create guidance for researchers that transforms the DDOMP into a living document with guides and templates on how to make decisions concerning creation and management of scientific data. We build upon the existing information provided by the Belmont Forum and created checklists for PIs to give their researchers to follow during the project, suggestions on how to communicate and use resources for better tracking of data and digital objects during the project. As a case

study, the PARSEC project has implemented these tools for the use of our researchers. This makes yearly reporting requirements much easier as well as communication across the team. We look forward to sharing these tools with the Global Collaboration on Data community.

3 Conclusions

This project, which exclusively uses existing data, has another two and a half years of life. We expect we shall need to adjust many plans along the way. By following open work practices where we can (we anticipate limitations on some of the socio-economic data), we intend to share what we learn along the way.

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